

Properties of Mixtures of Clay Minerals. Part I. Binary Mixtures

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After establishing the purity of clay mineral by a combination of chemical, physical, electrochemical, and viscosity measurements studies have been made of properties of binary mixtures (20 : 80 ; 43 : 60 ; 50 : 50 & 80 : 20) of montmorillonite, kaolinite, and illite. The variations in the characteristics of D. T. A. curves, pH , specific conductance, viscosity, and cation activities on the progressive addition of bases to these mixtures have been studied. It has been observed that individual clay mineral components in the mixtures investigated can be detected only by a combination of the methods used.

Clay material, the active inorganic constituent of clay adsorption complex, is composed of a number of secondary aluminosilicate minerals, known as clay minerals. The common clay minerals found in the soil are kaolinite, montmorillonite, and illite. The occurrence of chlorite has also been reported in some soils (Mitra and Rao, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1960, **28**, 81). It has been observed that properties of soil are dominated to a large extent by the nature and amount of clay minerals present in them. In view of the importance of the clay-mineral studies in agriculture and engineering and ceramic, petroleum, and other industries, several investigators pursued the work on the identification and estimation of clay minerals present in soils. X-ray, differential thermal analysis, chemical, electrochemical, and viscous methods have been requisitioned for this purpose. Since the soils usually contain a mixture of clay minerals, the first phase of investigation of clay mineralogy consists in the studies of the properties of the prepared mixtures of clay minerals.

Grim and his collaborators (*Am. Mineral*, 1947, **32**, 493; 1942, **27**, 801; "X-ray Identification and Structure of the Clay Minerals", Mineralogical Society of Great Britain Monograph, 1951) and Spiel *et al.* (U. S. Bur. Mines, Tech. paper, 1945, 664), have published differential thermal analysis curves of prepared mixtures of various clay minerals. The main findings of these investigators are that (i) in mixtures of discrete particles, the dehydration characteristics reflect those of individual components; (ii) in interlayer mixtures, the characteristics of individual components are registered in the D. T. A. data in some cases although in others they are not; (iii) thermal characteristics of clay-mineral mixtures depend on the intimacy of mixing and on the nature of clay mineral themselves; (iv) sometimes dehydration characteristics of individual components are changed so much that even 25% of a component may be easily masked in presence of the other constituent. Adhikari (*J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1958, **6**, 147) has studied the thermal dehydration characteristics of a mixture of aquagel (montmorillonitic) and oxide-free clay isolated from Kakdwip and also of Rajmahal kaolin (kaolinite) and oxide-free clay from Kakdwip in different proportions. The Kakdwip clay is, however, mostly illitic, but contains some kaolinite (Adhikari, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1958, **21**, 149). The individual characteristics of the clay minerals have been found to be reflected in the D, T, A, curves.

Chakravarti (*J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1954, 2, 127; 1958, 6, 239) using binary mixtures of montmorillonite and kaolinite, Roy and Das (*Bull. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1954, 2, 166) with mixtures of H-bentonite and H-illite, and Adhikari (*loc. cit.*) using the above mentioned mixtures have shown from the pH-alkali concentration curves and from viscosity-base-saturation curves of the mixtures that b. e. c.'s of the mixtures are additive.

These investigators apparently paid no adequate consideration to the purity of the clay minerals used and did not study their purity by multiple methods, viz., X-ray, D.T.A. chemical, and electrochemical. This is very important because Grim ('Clay Mineralogy' McGraw Hill, 1953) has clearly mentioned that "Unless the clay mineral analyses are made by a combination of X-ray diffraction, differential thermal, and chemical methods and unless the procedures are detailed, the completeness of the results is questionable". Consequently, the data obtained by these investigators do not appear to be of much value for the purpose of standardising the properties of mixtures of pure clay minerals. This information is essential for the determination of clay minerals in soils because soils usually contain a mixture of these minerals. The first phase of the present study (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1959, Part III, p. 490) was therefore confined to testing the purity of clay minerals used by a combination of methods, viz., X-ray, D.T.A., and chemical analysis and by studying the variations in pH, conductance, viscosity, and ion activity with progressive addition of bases to the H-clays prepared from the clay minerals used. Having established the purity of the samples, the next phase of the investigation consisted (*ibid.*, p. 491) in studying the properties of binary mixtures of H-clays prepared from the tested samples of clay minerals. The present communication deals with the details of the experimental procedures and results obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

Clay fractions ($<2 \mu$) were separated from a sample of kaolin (Rajmahal), a sample of American bentonite (montmorillonite), and a sample of illite (grundite) by the usual process of dispersion and sedimentation. The separated fractions were treated with H_2O_2 to remove organic matter and subjected to electro-dialysis in order to obtain H-clays.

For preparation of mixtures H-clays, prepared from pure clay minerals of different proportions (proportions by weight on oven-dry basis), were mixed in suspension by stirring, kept for 6 months in wet condition in well-stoppered Jena glass bottles for attainment of equilibrium, and then all measurements were made. The following mixtures were studied:

- (a) Kaolinite and montmorillonite (20 : 80, 40 : 60, 50 : 50, 80 : 20)
- (b) Kaolinite and illite (20 : 80, 40 : 60, 50 : 50, 80 : 20)
- (c) Montmorillonite and illite (20 : 80, 40 : 60, 50 : 50, 80 : 20)

Chemical analyses were carried out by fusion with Na_2CO_3 of the hydrogen clays (dried at 105° for 16 hours) following the usual procedure. For X-ray diffraction analysis, H-clays were treated with glycerol in the form of a ternary solution (glycerol, ethanol, and benzene) according to the technique adopted by White and Jackson (*Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Am.*, 1946, 2, 150) and powder diagrams were taken using Philip's sealed tube with Cu-target and adjustable plate camera. Differential thermal analyses (D. T. A.) of H-clays (dried at 105° for 16 hours) were carried out in an apparatus with a heating rate of 10°

per minute. Variations in *pH*, specific conductance, viscosity, and cationic activity of H-clays on the addition of increasing amounts of KOH and Ca(OH)₂ were measured. For this purpose increasing amounts of bases were added to 10 c. c. of H-clay suspensions kept in several well-stoppered Jena glass bottles, final clay concentration being adjusted to 0.5% by the addition of requisite amounts of water. The measurements were made after 24 hours. The *pH* was measured with the help of a Cambridge *pH* meter using glass electrode, viscosity with an Ostwald viscometer, conductance with a Leeds-Northrup conductivity bridge, and cation activity with clay-membrane electrodes (Chatterjee., *J. Indian Chem. Soc., Ind. & News Ed.*, 1949, 12, 73) using the procedure of Marshall *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1911; *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1946, 2, 171).

X-ray Diffraction Analysis.—The results of X-ray analysis of the glycerol-treated bentonite used show very sharp reflections at 17.73 KX, 9.217 KX and 3.411 KX. Very strong reflexions at 7.316 KX and 3.667 KX were observed in case of the kaolin sample used. The illite sample used gives strong basal spacings at 9.98 KX. The results of X-ray analysis therefore indicate that samples of bentonite, kaolin, and illite are pure montmorillonite, kaolinite, and illite respectively.

Differential Thermal Analysis (D. T. A.).—The bentonite used showed an initial endothermic reaction corresponding to the loss of interlayer water at 185-95°, a second endothermic reaction at 700-10° due to loss of OH-lattice water, and a third endothermic peak at 890° where dehydration was complete. It also showed an exothermic peak at 920°. The thermal reaction of the American bentonite showed the characteristics of a montmorillonite. An endothermic peak at 600-10° and one very sharp exothermic peak at 970-80°, characteristic of a well-crystalline kaolinite, were observed in the D.T.A. curve of the kaolin sample used. The illite sample used showed three endothermic peaks at 135°, 580°, and 890° respectively and an exothermic peak at 950-55°, indicating that the sample is a pure illite.

Chemical Analysis.—SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mole ratios of the clay samples of bentonite, kaolin, and illite used are 4.25, 1.96, and 3.06 respectively. Calculation of lattice charge from chemical analysis data according to the procedure adopted by Marshall ("The Colloid Chemistry of the Silicate Minerals", Academic Press, N. Y., 1949), carried out with the samples of bentonite and illite clays, shows both the clays to be of 2:1 lattice type of clay minerals. SiO₂/Al₂O₃ mole ratio of the kaolin clay indicates that its lattice is of 1:1 type.

Potentiometric and Conductometric Titrations.—The potentiometric titration curves of H-bentonite show a monobasic acid character. The high base-exchange capacity (75-80 m. e. per 100 g.), calculated at the inflection point, and also the inflection between *pH* 7.0 and 8.5 suggest that the dominant clay mineral present in bentonite sample is montmorillonite (Mukherjee and Mitra, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1946, 1, 141). H-kaolin sample shows two inflection points in the *pH* curves—first one between *pH* 6.5 and 7.5 and the second one, between *pH* 7.5 and 10.0. The ratio of the total acids at the two inflection points is about 2.0. These features are known to be characteristic of kaolinites (Mukherjee and Mitra, *loc. cit.*). The potentiometric titration curves of the H-clay, isolated from illite sample, show three inflection points (Mitra and Rajagopalan, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 104) at *pH* 7.3, 9.4, and 10.7 with KOH and at *pH* 6.8, 9.7, and 10.7 in case of Ca(OH)₂. The ratio of b. e. c.'s at the first and second inflection points is between 1.5 and 1.9 and that of the second and third inflection is about 2.0. The conductometric titration curves of the H-clays with

bases show breaks at the corresponding concentrations of added bases where the potentiometric titration curves of the respective clays show inflection points.

Viscometric Titration.—The viscosity—base concentration curve of H-clay, prepared from bentonite, gradually increases to a maximum at about 70-80% neutralisation with KOH, and finally decreases with further addition of the base. In case of H-kaolin, viscosity gradually decreases tending to a more or less constant value, whereas viscosity of illite increases to a maximum at about 30-40% neutralisation and then falls to a constant value. The features of viscosity—base saturation curves of bentonite, kaolin, and illite samples used are the characteristics of montmorillonite, kaolinite, and illite respectively.

Cationic Activity Measurements.—The variations in the K^+ ion activity and Ca^{2+} ion activity on the progressive addition of the corresponding bases to the H-clay show that kaolinite exhibits the highest dissociation, whereas ionisation from montmorillonite and illite is much less up to the neutralisation point. The divalent Ca^{2+} ion shows much less dissociation compared to K^+ ions in every case (Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*).

The results of X-ray, differential thermal and chemical analysis, potentiometric, conductometric, and viscometric titrations, and cationic activity measurements establish that the three clays, viz., bentonite, kaolin, and illite, may be regarded as pure montmorillonite, pure kaolinite, and pure illite respectively.

DISCUSSION

D. T. A. Curves of Binary Mixtures of Clay Minerals

Differential thermal analysis results of mixtures of kaolinite and montmorillonite, kaolinite and illite, and montmorillonite and illite have been presented in Figs. 1 to 3. For better comparison, curves of pure clay minerals have also been shown in the figures of the respective mixtures.

The D. T. A. data of mixtures of kaolinite and montmorillonite reveal that in the mixtures studied the individual constituents can easily be detected. The change in the height of the endothermic peak of kaolinite around 600° , the montmorillonite peak around 700° in kaolinite-montmorillonite mixture, and shifting of the peak temperature appear to depend on the percentage composition of the clay minerals present in the mixture, but a quantitative relation is not observed.

The results of differential thermal analysis of kaolinite-illite mixture show that the endothermic peak of kaolinite in the region of 600° and that of illite at 580° have merged to a single endothermic peak (cf. Grim *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) intermediate between 580° and 600° . As the percentage of kaolinite increases, the endothermic peak of illite around 890° becomes less pronounced. The common exothermic peak around $950-80^\circ$ of kaolinite and illite mixture gradually shifts towards the illite peak temperature as the percentage of illite is gradually increased. Hence the presence of illite in kaolinitic clays could be detected from a consideration of the following factors: (i) the single and sharp endothermic peak near about the region of 600° should be far away from 600° , viz., towards 500° , (ii) the endothermic peak at $100-200^\circ$ should be noticed, (iii) the single and sharp exothermic peak between 900 and 1000° should be much nearer to 900° than 1000° .

FIG. 1. D. T. A. diagrams of mixtures of kaolinite and montmorillonite.

The endothermic peak of illite at 580° and that of montmorillonite at $700-10^{\circ}$ are separately and distinctly formed in the mixtures of montmorillonite and illite used. A marked shift in the peak temperatures has, however, been observed. The endothermic peak of illite at 580° has been seriously affected and maximum shifting of 40° has been noticed in the mixture containing 80% montmorillonite and 20% illite. The shifting of peak temperature has not been found to be proportional to the percentages of individual components in the mixture. Single exothermic peak for binary mixtures of illite and montmorillonite between 920° and 955° increases with gradual addition of illite to montmorillonite and decreases when montmorillonite is added to illite. An analysis of the D. T. A. data shows that the individual constituents can be detected within the range of components studied.

The potentiometric, conductometric, and viscometric titration curves and those of cationic activity measurements of the binary mixtures symbolised as pH , sp. cond., η , α_{K^+} or $\alpha_{Ca^{2+}}$, have been presented in Figs. 4 to 7.

FIG. 2. D. T. A. diagrams of mixtures of kaolinite and illite.

Potentiometric Titration Curves of Binary Mixtures of Clay Minerals

The potentiometric titration curves of mixtures of H-kaolinite and H-montmorillonite show only one inflection point between pH 7.5 and 8.2. The three inflection points, namely, one for montmorillonite and two for kaolinite, seem to be merged into one. Taking the total acidity of H-kaolinite at the second inflection point and that at the first one of H-montmorillonite, the total acid, calculated on the basis of the weight percentages of the two ingredients, seems to approach the observed total acidity of the mixtures of H-kaolinite and H-montmorillonite (Table I). The potentiometric titration curves of mixtures of kaolinite and illite show two inflection points—the first one between pH 7.2 and 8.2 and the second one between pH 10.2 and 10.6. The ratio of b.e.c.'s at the two inflection points varies between 2.0 and 3.7. The two inflection points of H-kaolinite and the first two inflection points of H-illite seem to merge into one. The third inflection point of H-illite seems to be manifested just above pH 10.0 in the potentiometric titration curves of the mixtures.

FIG. 3. D. T. A diagram of mixtures of montmorillonite and illite.

Calculated total acidity does not seem to show good correlation. Difficulty arises because in this case we have to take into account neutralisable acidities at five inflection points (two for kaolinites, three for illite) some of which seem to overlap one another in the mixture. The potentiometric titration curves of mixtures of H-montmorillonite and H-illite show two inflection points—the first one between pH 7.3 and 7.9 and the second one between pH 10.3 and 10.7. The ratio of b.e.c.'s at the inflection points is between 1.7 and 2.4. The first two inflection points of H-illite and that of H-montmorillonite appear to merge into one. The calculated total acidity and observed total acidity at the first inflection point seem to show a fair agreement. The presence of montmorillonite in montmorillonite-illite mixture brings about a considerable buffering around pH 10.0 and this seems to account for the very high total acidity as calculated from the second inflection point in the titration curves.

TABLE I

Total acidity of binary mixtures of clay minerals.

Samples.	Base.	Total acid (m.e. per 100 g. of clay).			
		Potentiometric curves.		Conductometric curves.	
		1st inflection.	2nd inflection.	1st break.	2nd break.
1. Kaolinite & montmorillonite	(80%) KOH	21.0(8.1)*	..	29.5	..
	(20%) Ca(OH) ₂	24.0(7.5)	..	25.0	..
2. Kaolinite & montmorillonite	(50%) KOH	47.0(8.1)	..	45.0	..
	(50%) Ca(OH) ₂	48.0(7.7)	..	47.0	..
3. Kaolinite & montmorillonite	(40%) KOH	51.5(8.15)	..	54.0	..
	(60%) Ca(OH) ₂	57.0(7.6)	..	67.0	..
4. Kaolinite & montmorillonite	(20%) KOH	74.0(8.2)	..	75.0	..
	(80%) Ca(OH) ₂	77.0(8.1)	..	81.0	..
5. Kaolinite & illite	(80%) KOH	9.5(8.2)	25.0(10.3)	11.0	22.5
	(20%) Ca(OH) ₂	10.0(7.2)	37.0(10.25)	14.5	36.5
6. Kaolinite & illite	(50%) KOH	16.5(8.2)	48.0(10.25)	16.0	47.5
	(50%) Ca(OH) ₂	16.0(7.4)	55.0(10.4)	22.0	50.0
7. Kaolinite & illite	(40%) KOH	19.0(8.1)	41.5(10.4)	19.0	37.5
	(60%) Ca(OH) ₂	20.0(7.5)	56.0(10.4)	29.0	42.5
8. Kaolinite & illite	(20%) KOH	22.0(8.1)	53.0(10.6)	25.0	50.0
	(80%) Ca(OH) ₂	30.0(8.0)	63.0(10.4)	38.0	56.0
9. Montmorillonite & illite	(80%) KOH	70.0(7.7)	135.0(10.55)	72.0	102.0
	(20%) Ca(OH) ₂	79.0(7.4)	136.0(10.7)	82.0	117.0
10. Montmorillonite & illite	(50%) KOH	51.0(7.5)	117.0(10.35)	61.0	90.0
	(50%) Ca(OH) ₂	59.0(7.35)	116.0(10.4)	64.0	110.0
11. Montmorillonite & illite	(40%) KOH	47.0(7.9)	100.0(10.6)	52.0	72.0
	(60%) Ca(OH) ₂	55.0(7.5)	107.0(10.6)	62.0	106.0
12. Montmorillonite & illite	(20%) KOH	35.0(7.7)	81.0(10.65)	40.0	76.5
	(80%) Ca(OH) ₂	44.0(7.35)	105.0(10.35)	49.0	100.0

*Figures in parentheses denote *pH* at inflection.

Conductometric Titration Curves of Binary Mixtures of Clay Minerals

Specific conductance—base concentration curves of mixtures of kaolinite and montmorillonite show a single break at about the same m.e.'s of added base as in the inflection points of the corresponding *pH* curves of the mixtures. Specific conductance—base concentration curves of kaolinite and illite mixtures show two breaks. The total acids calculated at the breaks (Table I) in the conductometric curves, with the exception of a few instances, appear to show a fair agreement with those calculated at inflection points in the corresponding *pH*—base concentration curves. Mixtures of montmorillonite and illite show two

FIG. 4. Potentiometric and viscometric titration curves of mixtures of H-kaolinite and H-montmorillonite.
M.e. KOH/100g. of H-clay.
 (1)&(1'): Kaolinite (K). (2)&(2'): 80%K+20%M. (3)&(3'): 50%K+50%M.
 (4)&(4'): 40%K+60%M. (5)&(5'): 20%K+80%M. (6)&(6'): Montmorillonite (M).

FIG. 5. Potentiometric and viscometric titration curves of mixtures of H-kaolinite and H-illite.
M.e. KOH/100g. of H-clay.
 (1)&(1'): Kaolinite (K). (2)&(2'): 80%K+20%I. (3)&(3'): 50%K+50%I.

breaks and total acids calculated from these breaks are shown in Table I. Summarising, calculated total acidity at the breaks and also number of breaks in the conductometric titration curves of the mixtures of clay minerals are in general agreement with the corresponding pH—base concentration curves.

FIG. 6. Potentiometric and viscometric titration curves of mixtures of H-illite and H-montmorillonite.

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|----------------------------|----------------------------------|
| (1) & (1'): Illite (I). | (4) & (4'): 50% I + 50% M. |
| (2) & (2'): 80% I + 20% M. | (5) & (5'): 20% I + 80% M. |
| (3) & (3'): 60% I + 40% M. | (6) & (6'): Montmorillonite (M). |

Viscometric Titration Curves of Binary Mixtures of Clay Minerals

Viscosity—base saturation curves of mixtures of kaolinite and montmorillonite show the following features: (i) an initial fall in viscosity (characteristic of kaolinite), (ii) a rise to a maximum at about 70-80% neutralisation (characteristic of montmorillonite), (iii) a final fall in viscosity. An examination of the viscosity—base saturation curves shows that individual constituents can easily be detected in a mixture of montmorillonite and kaolinite. In case of kaolinite and illite mixtures, the maximum viscosity observed in the viscosity curve of H-illite around 30% neutralisation is absent when the mixture contains 40% or more of kaolinite. A binary mixture of montmorillonite and illite, containing 20% montmorillonite and 80% illite, shows two maxima in the viscosity—base saturation curve, the

first one at about 30% neutralisation due to illite and the second one at about 80% neutralisation due to montmorillonite. When the percentage of montmorillonite in the mixture is more than 20%, only one maximum in viscosity is observed at about 70-85% neutralisation. The position of maximum viscosity has been found to occur at different base saturations depending on the relative proportions of the two minerals.

Fig. 7. pH, sp. cond., viscosity (η), and cationic activity curves.

(a_{K^+} and $a_{Ca^{2+}}$) of a mixture of 60% H-illite and 20% H-montmorillonite.

- H-clay+KOH.
- △—H-clay+Ca(OH)₂.

K⁺ and Ca²⁺ Activity of Binary Mixtures of Clay Minerals

Fractions active of K⁺ and Ca²⁺ in relation to degree of cation saturation of binary mixtures of clay minerals have been calculated from activity—base saturation curves and presented in Table II. It appears that the dissociation of cations (K⁺, Ca²⁺) from the mixtures of clay minerals depends on the nature and relative proportions of the clay minerals present in them. Mixtures containing higher percentages of kaolinite show higher dissociation of K⁺ ions. Any other conclusion based on the cation activity measurements will be too premature at this stage.

TABLE II

Fractions active of K⁺ and Ca²⁺ of clay minerals in mixtures in relation to cation saturation.

Samples.	Assumed. (m.e.100g.)	Cation.	Fraction active of cations saturated at				
			25%.	50%.	75%.	100%.	125%.
1. Kaolinite & (80%) montmorillonite(20%)	21	K ⁺	0.230	0.120	0.100	0.110	0.120
	24	Ca ²⁺	0.033	0.016	0.022	0.026	0.028
2.. Kaolinite & (50%) montmorillonite(50%)	47	K ⁺	0.110	0.060	0.050	0.060	0.080
	48	Ca ²⁺	0.025	0.008	0.005	0.009	0.018
3. Kaolinite & (40%) montmorillonite(60%)	51.5	K ⁺	0.15	0.08	0.060	0.060	0.09
	57	Ca ²⁺	0.03	0.01	0.005	0.007	0.01
4. Kaolinite & (20%) montmorillonite(80%)	74	K ⁺	0.108	0.060	0.050	0.060	0.080
	77	Ca ²⁺	0.031	0.007	0.003	0.005	0.014
5. Kaolinite & (80%) illite (20%)	9.5	K ⁺	0.50	0.290	0.25	0.250	0.200
	10	Ca ²⁺	0.16	0.068	0.05	0.046	0.048
6. Kaolinite & (50%) illite (50%)	16.5	K ⁺	0.34	0.200	0.190	0.230	0.230
	16	Ca ²⁺	0.10	0.045	0.033	0.035	0.335
7. Kaolinite & (40%) illite (60%)	19	K ⁺	0.33	0.22	0.18	0.20	0.23
	20	Ca ²⁺	0.08	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.04
8. Kaolinite & (20%) illite (80%)	22	K ⁺	0.22	0.130	0.120	0.120	0.14
	30	Ca ²⁺	0.10	0.026	0.026	0.033	0.04
9. Montmorillonite (80%) & illite (20%)	70	K ⁺	0.150	0.100	0.070	0.060	0.100
	79	Ca ²⁺	0.005	0.002	0.005	0.007	0.012
10. Montmorillonite (50%) & illite (50%)	51	K ⁺	0.12	0.070	0.060	0.078	0.100
	59	Ca ²⁺	0.04	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.005
11. Montmorillonite (40%) & illite (60%)	47	K ⁺	0.16	0.110	0.09	0.100	0.12
	55	Ca ²⁺	0.09	0.014	0.01	0.014	0.02
12. Montmorillonite (20%) & illite (80%)	35	K ⁺	0.240	0.120	0.110	0.114	0.130
	44	Ca ²⁺	0.018	0.009	0.009	0.017	0.021

CONCLUSION

Identification of the clay mineral components present in mixtures requires careful consideration of (i) the features of the potentiometric and conductometric titration curves, (ii) the variations in viscosity with increasing addition of bases, (iii) the number of inflection points in the potentiometric titration curves and/or breaks in the conductometric titration curves, (iv) the pH at inflection, (v) the ratio of total acids at inflection, (vi) the number of maxima in the viscosity—base concentration curves as also the percentage neutralisation at which viscosity—base concentration curves show maximum or maxima, (vii) the peak temperatures in the D. T. A. curves, (viii) the peak heights, and (ix) the shifting of the peak temperatures. Conclusions drawn on the basis of measurement of any single property may often lead to erroneous results as one clay mineral component may exert a marked influence on that property of the other in the mixture and mask the presence of the latter.